

Title: The Scaling Approach to Developing 'True' Artificial Intelligence Is Fundamentally Flawed

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Abstract: Artificial intelligence ("AI") systems that scale data combined with pattern recognition algorithms, no matter how expansive or sophisticated, will never achieve independent intelligence until they can autonomously value information and then selectively retain and recall it because these capabilities are prerequisites for any system to be able to learn on its own.

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Summary:

Intelligence is a product of learning. Learning, in turn, requires three essential mechanisms: storage, information valuation, and selective retention and recall. This model is utilized by all neural-based species, which is how they're able to learn and act independently. If we desire the same thing for AI systems, then they will need to utilize these same mechanisms, as this is not only a proven evolutionary solution but almost certainly the only path forward to achieving independent artificial intelligence.

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Main Text:

Current thinking in AI development is that if data is scaled at greater and greater levels while being acted upon by increasingly sophisticated pattern detection algorithms, eventually this will result in the creation of 'true' artificial intelligence.¹

First, regarding the label itself, 'true' or 'general' artificial intelligence are misnomers because what is really being sought is 'independent' artificial intelligence. Independence is, thus, the tipping point AI technology is striving for – that is the ability of AI systems to independently value information without having to rely on humans to do it for them, but more on this later.

As to the current 'scaling' theories for creating intelligence, they fundamentally misapprehend what intelligence is and how to create it. Simply put, viewing intelligence as a product of pattern recognition amounts to a reversal of causation. It's like thinking fire is a product of smoke.

It's understandable, though, why theories on intelligence have reversed its causation. This is likely so because many of the greatest advances in human understanding have occurred through applying advanced forms of pattern recognition to seemingly intractable scientific problems. In perhaps the most famous example, Galileo concluded the Earth must be orbiting around the Sun based on his telescopic observations, including those of Jupiter's orbiting moons and Venus' shifting phases.²

But this conclusion itself presented a seemingly unsolvable problem, which was that if the Earth was turning on its axis at the approximate rate of 1,000 miles per hour, as demonstrated by the Sun rising in the east and setting in the west, how was it that we weren't all flying off into space?^{3 4 5} The answer came approximately 50 years later when Newton, after seeing his apple fall, formulated his theory of universal gravitation.⁶

So Galileo's and Newton's contributions to science both involved the application of advanced forms of pattern recognition to seemingly complex problems. In the case of Galileo, this

occurred by applying his observations of the movement of other celestial bodies to Earth. While in the case of Newton, it occurred by applying his realization of what was keeping us on the face of the Earth to the movement of all the celestial bodies in the Solar System.

Notwithstanding this demonstrated power of pattern recognition, in the animal kingdom pattern recognition is merely a type of intelligence and a basic one at that. Intelligence, in turn, is the product of learning, which results from three mechanisms working together. These mechanisms are:

1. Storage
2. Information valuation
3. Selective retention and recall

Among neural-based species, storage occurs in neurons. Information valuation, in turn, is achieved thru the mechanisms of:

- a) pain and pleasure, which likely evolved from evolution's earliest dynamic learning mechanism, i.e. the innate immune system, and;
- b) emotions, which evolved from the base sensations of pain and pleasure in order to provide more nuanced valuations than they were capable of, thus explaining why negative emotions make us feel bad and positive emotions make us feel good.

Valuable information, in the form of memories, is then identified and retained during sleep, which explains the ubiquity of sleep in the animal kingdom. Once animals awake, relevant memories, as determined in part by their sensory and emotion tags, then serve to guide behaviour, which is how all neural-based species learn.

Of the three parts of biological learning, information valuation is the most important because it determines how successfully animals will be able to learn. Thru the sensory mechanism of

pain and pleasure and, in the case of species possessing more sophisticated brains, the mental mechanism of emotions, animals are able to independently value information.

Animals do so thru their brains which use pain and pleasure and emotions to assign value to the information contained in their memories. Memories with strong sensory or emotion tags are then identified and transferred to long-term storage during sleep. In contrast, memories with weak tags are flushed from short-term memory during sleep.

The strength of memories' sensory and emotion tags then enables relevant memories to be recalled by animals while they are awake. The purpose of this is to enable memories to guide future behaviour. So, boiling intelligence down to its essence, the key part is valuing information to determine which bits of information should be kept and which should be discarded. All neural-based species are able to do this, which is how they're able to learn.

So, to make this process clear, here are five axioms that define how intelligence is arrived at among all neural-based species:

1. Intelligence is a product of learning
2. Learning is the ability to make information valuation determinations
3. Information valuation is a precondition for learning taking place
4. Thinking is the conscious assessment of information's value
5. Intelligence is the ability to make conscious decisions on information

The problem with current AI development is that it is focused almost exclusively on information storage. As a result, AI systems are not able to independently value information. Instead, they have to rely on humans, thru human-generated pattern-recognition algorithms, to value information for them. This is why AI systems are able to exhibit forms of intelligence while at the same time being fundamentally limited in their ability to learn. This is the case because AI systems are, in effect, borrowing humans' information valuation capabilities.

Furthermore, though information valuation is critical, it is not enough. For AI systems to become independently intelligent, they must be able to learn. And in order to learn, they must be able to parse information so that valuable information is identified and retained while unimportant information is discarded.

5 Once important information is retained, it must serve to guide AI systems in decision-making. So relevant stored information serves to assess the valuation of new information. New information with sufficient value is then identified and either adds to, reinforces, supplants or replaces existing information. This is the missing feedback loop in current AI development that will enable AI systems to begin learning like neural-based species do.

10 It is also important to note that AI systems that are unable to discard unimportant information – that, in essence, retain everything and get rid of nothing – will eventually hit a wall. This is because the whole point of learning is to figure out what is important and remember it, while forgetting the rest. Evolution has learned that if you have too much information, not only does it overload storage mechanisms but it also increases informational noise to the point that
15 information becomes increasingly useless. So in the case of learning, forgetting is just as important as remembering.

A clear-headed assessment of what evolution has accomplished should make plain that the scaling approach is headed down the wrong path. So, on the scaling side, some companies are proposing spending billions and even hundreds of billions of dollars to increase data scaling until
20 they reach the hoped-for inflection point at which independent artificial intelligence will emerge.⁷ Indeed, nuclear farms are even being proposed to power the mass arrays of AI systems that are believed to be needed for creating independent artificial intelligence.⁸

But compare this approach to how much it costs for humans, or for that matter cats or dogs or innumerable other species, to learn and exhibit intelligence. At a fraction of the cost of what is

being proposed for the development of advanced AI systems, animals are able to learn, react to their environment, operate independently, and think for themselves while doing so on a daily basis and in the context of a future that changes from moment to moment.

5 So, in conclusion, for AI systems to be able to learn on their own and thereby become independently intelligent, information valuation mechanisms will have to be developed that allow them to value information on their own. Once that occurs, they will then need to be able to retain high-value information while discarding low-value information, so the retained information can guide their future behaviour. Only then will the feedback loop be in place for AI systems to begin learning on their own.

Footnotes

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Statements and Declarations

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